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RETROSPECTIVE EXCURSUS INTO HOSPITALITY TRADITIONS AS A MEANS OF EXPANDING OPPORTUNITIES FOR SINGLE AREAS MARKETING

Abstract. *This paper is devoted to the consideration of some directions of development of the Russian tourism and hospitality industry in the modern period of quite serious challenges. Nowadays tourism industry seems to be a very significant part in socio-economic and political discussion, so the undertaken study is relevant enough. The authors analyze various internal and external aspects affecting the tourism and hospitality industry. Options for improving the attractiveness of internal resources of the impressions industry are proposed to expand the marketing capabilities of single areas, including the use of a retrospective into the traditions of hospitality. The authors also consider potential opportunities of the Russian Federation policy in the development of the tourism industry. In addition, the study pays special attention to the analysis of some problems that slow down the development of the tourism and hospitality industry of single areas. In difficult geopolitical conditions, the actualization of retrospective opportunities of single areas is essentially a strategic potential for the development of domestic tourism. Ultimately, the authors state that a retrospective excursus into the traditions of hospitality at the present stage can help to expand marketing opportunities and to improve the efficiency of the economic component of individual regions and will allow, through an appeal to the past, to influence the present in such a way as to promote the preservation of the national identity of single areas, which is an undoubted dominant in the formation and preservation of the self-identity of the nation.*

Keywords: *single areas, traditions of hospitality, retrospective excursus, marketing, historical and cultural heritage sites, domestic tourism*

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РЕТРОЭККУРС В ТРАДИЦИИ ГОСТЕПРИИМСТВА КАК СРЕДСТВО РАСШИРЕНИЯ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЕЙ МАРКЕТИНГА МОНОТЕРРИТОРИЙ

Исследование посвящено рассмотрению некоторых направлений развития российской индустрии туризма и гостеприимства в современный период достаточно серьёзных вызовов. В настоящее время туристская отрасль представляется весьма значимым актором социально-экономического и политического дискурсов, поэтому актуальность предпринятого исследования не вызывает сомнений. В исследовательском поле авторов оказываются различные внутренние и внешние детерминанты, способные воздействовать на индустрию туризма и гостеприимства. Предлагаются варианты совершенствования привлекательности внутренних ресурсов индустрии впечатлений для расширения возможностей маркетинга монотерриторий, в том числе через ретроэкскурсы в традиции гостеприимства. Вместе с тем рассматриваются потенциальные возможности внутренней политики субъектов РФ в развитии туристской отрасли. Кроме того, в исследовании уделяется особое внимание анализу некоторых проблем, замедляющих развитие индустрии туризма и гостеприимства монотерриторий. В непростых геополитических условиях актуализация ретроэкскурсионных возможностей монотерриторий является по сути стратегическим потенциалом для развития внутреннего туризма. В конечном итоге авторы приходят к выводу, что ретроэкскурс в традиции гостеприимства на современном этапе будет способствовать не только расширению возможностей маркетинга и повышению эффективности экономической составляющей отдельных регионов, но и, в свою очередь, позволит через обращение к прошлому оказать влияние на настоящее таким образом, чтобы содействовать сохранению национальной самобытности монотерриторий, которая является несомненной доминантой в формировании и сохранении самоидентичности нации.

Ключевые слова: *монотерритории, традиции гостеприимства, ретроэкскурс, маркетинг, объекты историко-культурного наследия, внутренний туризм*

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Introduction

In the modern world, service is a multi-component system that includes various services, in which tourism and hotel business are important components, since they are vectors of development of the world and national economy and contribute to the economic stability of single-zone regions. It is impossible to develop an effective strategy for the hotel business without a competent scientific approach to this area of services. A retrospective excursus into the tradition of hospitality is, in fact, an expansion of the "management horizon" in the direction of actively promoting "nostalgic tourism" to meet the need to restore physical strength and renew moral through the activation of emotional connections, through a journey to your homeland, to your origins, to the "clean slate". The implementation of this research direction is due, on the one hand, to the "cultural globalization" of the modern world, which contributes to the desire of a person to "touch" the unique, original, valuable, and on the other hand, - the "cultural split" observed recently in society, partly due to the unstable political situation. At the same time, the appeal to a calmer and more carefree past is caused by the current lack of a sense of security and the constant escalation of fears for the fate of the country and the world as a whole. Therefore, today the tourism and hospitality industry, engaged in retro-excursion marketing, can very well "capitalize" the "nostalgic need" of the modern traveler, thereby diversifying the possibilities of single areas.

The aim of the research proposed within the framework of this article is a retrospective analysis of the compositional structure and content of the concept of "hospitality traditions", which act as one of the means of "expanding" the possibilities of the single territories marketing opportunities in conditions of increasing crisis components.

Methods and methodology.

Analysis of publications on research issues

The development of a scientific methodology that provides for the integrated use of both general scientific and special groups of methods allowed, within the framework of this study, to

update the most effective ways of using retro objects in the tourism industry in modern realities. Enrichment of tourist content with tourist objects, one way or another affiliated with the past, will not only make regional and national travel more original, but will also significantly contribute to the economic well-being of specific single areas.

The increase in quantitative indicators of scientific research reflecting the specifics of domestic tourism development in the Russian Federation today confirms the needs of the scientific community to study the most pressing aspects of the tourism industry. The interest in a retrospective excursus into the tradition of hospitality is evidenced by the relevant scientific works of tourism specialists, which, in turn, is consistent with the opinion of Deliy & Kulgachev about tourism as "... a driver of the regional and national economies" and its "multiplier effect in economic growth" [4, p. 116]. A. V. Karev, who considers new trends and opportunities for domestic tourism development (under conditions of external restrictions), considers it possible to coordinate investments in regional potential, taking into account the possibilities for developing the most promising types of tourism in them [6, 96]. The study by N. Yu. Chausova & A. S. Yemeleva [15, 208] is devoted to identifying and assessing the indicators that determine the main directions and growth of tourist flow. An important niche within the framework of social practices of spatial mobility is represented by domestic tourism of the Russian Federation in the work of K. M. Kerimi & O. V. Lysikova, who propose a systemic "pool of measures in a strategy with foresight thinking" for developing a range of constructive directions of tourist and recreational destinations capable of overcoming socio-economic barriers and political restrictions [7, p. 45]. Author's tours in the regions, introducing tourists to insufficiently known objects (and not only to popular ones), are in the focus of A. A. Nikiforova [10, p. 226]. The relevance of the regional approach to the tourism sector in the Russian Federation is stated by G. M. Safina, who also notes that tourism currently "...has turned into a significant planetary socio-

economic and political phenomenon" [12, p. 48]. The development of an author's tour "Traveling through the Largest Cities of Russia" is proposed in the publication of V. V. Lavrov [8, p. 51]. "The multiplier effect of operational activities", according to S. N. Pozdeeva & I. V. Zaychikova, gives the tourism industry a special uniqueness [11, p. 97]. According to N. V. Ivanova & N. I. Osipova, the tourism market needs to show flexibility to adapt to new trends in the tourism industry [5, p. 120].

Discussion

Many processes occurring in the modern world are often, to one degree or another, conditioned by connections with the past and include in their content numerous variables and constants that abound in such meanings and functions that can sometimes be understood only by specialists or a limited circle of people interested in Russian history, culture, their interrelations and interactions. Therefore, today (in the post-pandemic period and the period of particular increase in geopolitical tensions), it seems more important and timely than ever for all interested parties to turn to the development of domestic tourism (especially its retro-excursion component), since it is precisely this that is, at the present stage, essentially the only possible option for solving the problem of people's needs for recreation, rest, and a complete "reboot". As Yu. Sevryukov & V. Z. Shurbe argue, "tourism in the context of modern, unprecedented difficulties and restrictions can be considered as an internal reserve and direction for the development of recreation in Russia" [13, p. 354].

The sanctions pressure in various spheres of activity, to which the country has been subjected in recent years, has had a significant impact on the tourism industry: significant adjustments have been made to the work of transport, catering establishments, and organizations responsible for the accommodation, recreation, and entertainment of travelers. For obvious reasons, income from the tourism business has changed and

turned out to be significantly lower than previous values. Of course, tourism is a branch of the economy that cannot develop equally throughout the country, which is due to geographical, climatic, and historical factors.

The cardinal changes that have occurred in various areas of life and activity, affecting both the economy, politics, and the social sphere, have transformed the tourism industry: the changes have affected logistics solutions, and recreational and leisure programs, and the organization of services at public catering establishments. As a result, the profit from the tourism industry has changed dramatically, which, in turn, has affected not only regional economic development, but also the situation in the country as a whole. Authoritative economic regulators note the "imbalance" of economic growth in the country, its variability, i.e. the dynamics of demand does not correspond to the possibilities of supply of goods and services. The economic situation in the country is affected by both stable (inflation) and "volatile" components (rising prices for marker goods: fruits and vegetables, gasoline, dairy products) ¹. In addition, the economic situation in the country is affected by groups of internal and external conditions. The first group of conditions includes: logistical problems and cross-border payments, a slowdown in the growth rate of investment and consumer activity, which has caused the indicators of current business climate assessments to move into negative values, etc. The second group of conditions primarily includes: a possible increase in geopolitical pressure; a slowdown in global economic growth; a drop in demand for raw materials, which in the long term could have a negative impact on Russian exports, and through them on the Russian currency. All this together has a dual effect on various sectors of the economy, including domestic tourism, which is in dire need of modernizing the local management system, ranking the capabilities of the business community associated with the tourism industry,

¹ Statement by the Chairman of the Bank of Russia Elvira Nabiullina following the meeting of the Board of Directors of the Bank of Russia on September 13, 2024. URL: <https://cbr.ru/press/event/?id=20993> (Date of access 09.27.2024)

using underutilized and opening up new domestic tourism resources in order to increase the investment attractiveness of the industry locally, etc.

What is happening in the world today has quite clearly illustrated the fact that it is precisely domestic tourism content that can give new impetus to the economic development of both individual states as a whole and single areas (Table 1).

Table 1 – Tourism and the world economy

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
World GDP of the tourism and travel sector in % of the previous year	103.5	49.6	121.7	7.6	23.3
Number of jobs in the tourism sector, million units	333	271	289	295.4	319.6
as a % of the total number of jobs in the world	10.0	8.3	9.1	9.0	8.2
Investments in fixed capital in tourism, billion USD	986.2	693.2	...	855.9	954.3
as a % of the total investment	4.4	3.2	...	3.2	11.5

Today, hospitality industry professionals are seeing a significant decrease in tourism industry profits (around seven billion USD). At the same time, in Russia, the opposite situation has been observed in recent years: domestic tourism revenues have been increasing. In 2023, tourism profits in Russia amounted to 280 billion rubles, which is 2.3 times more than in 2019².

Domestic tourism has become a key trend over the past two years and is likely to remain so in the near future. In this regard, in the period from 2020 to 2023, many regions of Russia made a number of decisions to invest in its development. Most experts and even ordinary citizens understand that in such conditions, it will be extremely difficult for the industry to quickly

recover and return to its usual rhythm of life. In the current situation in the Russian Federation, there is an increased demand for domestic tourist destinations and facilities within the country, which has been recorded by the regions of the South of Russia since 2020, including Crimea and the Krasnodar Territory, in the republics of the North Caucasus – Dagestan, Chechnya, Adygea, etc., as well as regions of Siberia, the Far East, Primorye, etc. [14, p. 75].

Tourism as part of modern domestic economic processes has a constantly changing set of specifications, which can be conditionally divided into two groups – general and specific. General ones include the type of visa regime when crossing borders and their transparency, the creation of conditions of the most favorable treatment or, on the contrary, strict restrictions at the state and interstate levels, and specific ones include the growth of geopolitical contradictions, the expansion of the sanctions list for the Russian state. In this regard, domestic tourism at the present stage acquires some features characteristic of specific countries (Fig. 1).

Tourism companies (both global and Russian) have recently repeatedly changed their priorities in their work. In 2023, the so-called "neighbor tourism" is becoming quite popular, which means weekend trips to neighboring regions and the Near Abroad. In the Russian Federation, interest in "neighbor tourism" is especially noticeable in the Far East – up to 50% of all trips fall on this segment. At the same time, tourists from the Stavropol Territory and Rostov Region choose trips to the Caucasus Mountains, etc. And this is understandable: it is much easier to bring neighbors to yourself than to engage in "large-scale marketing" throughout Russia. Of the Near Abroad countries, the most popular are Belarus, Armenia, Kazakhstan and some others. "Event tourism" does not go unnoticed by travel lovers (the growth in this segment is 7-10% year on year). In this regard, there is a growing interest in

²Siluanov, A. G. The profit of the Russian tourism industry in 2023 amounted to almost 280 billion rubles. URL: <https://tass.ru/ekonomika/20386821> (Date of access 09.07.2024)

Altai, the Russian North, Murmansk and Kamchatka (they are partly attracted by the fact that you can combine active recreation with getting to know local attractions). The presented reorientation of tourist flows is due not only to increasing "geopolitical risks", but also to the lack of stability

in terms of solvency, which has had a serious impact on the consumer behavior of modern travelers, although Turkey, which has enjoyed active demand in recent years, has not become an outsider either (in 2023, it accounted for more than a quarter of all summer trips by Russians).

Fig. 1 – Methods and techniques for stimulating domestic tourism

Today, a number of countries actively encourage the development of domestic tourism: according to the WTO, domestic tourism currently accounts for about 75% of travelers' spending. For example, in the Italian Republic, hotel services were subsidized in the post-pandemic period. In turn, "digital aggregators" began to actively promote programs of ready-made domestic routes on the relevant travel service websites. Vouchers with discounts on tourist trips were offered to residents of Malaysia. The hashtag "This summer I am visiting France" became popular in the French Republic: the French essentially became "ambassadors" of domestic travel. The Argentine Republic stepped up the promotion of domestic tourism using media resources: not only webinars and meetings with entrepreneurs were held, but numerous press tours were also organized for

local journalists. In addition, to attract interest in traveling around the country, appropriate agreements were concluded with digital aggregators and bloggers. All these measures ultimately increased the number of tourists by 20%. Greece managed to stimulate the tourist flow due to discounts for the poor and additional payments from the state to hoteliers. The Federative Republic of Brazil actively supported its tourism industry during the pandemic, paying quite decent amounts of benefits to employees of the tourism industry and providing tax breaks to these enterprises, and hoteliers provided clients with discounts of up to 10%. As a result of such support, the domestic flow increased by almost a third. The Kingdom of Spain provided its citizens with a discount of up to 50% on tourism services and hotel accommodation in the post-pandemic period. Residents of the

United States of America significantly increased (about 70%) the number of trips within the country in the post-pandemic period, which is associated with some benefits for them (for example, a "tax deduction" was allowed on expenses during trips around the country). Many tourists began to directly book accommodation more often and use the services of aggregators.

Currently, another "new trend" in the tourism industry is the digitalization of travel, which allows not only to independently coordinate a virtual route, but also to use audio resources (mobile applications, audio guides, etc.) when constructing original excursions. As noted by experts in the field under study, "... the digitalization of domestic tourism offers the sector, among other things, the opportunity to create "deferred demand" by focusing on the retrospective resources of individual national monotourisms" [16, p. 132]. According to various analysts, approximately a third of the tourism industry market in the Russian Federation appeals to digital services today. This allows for the active use of retrospective resources of individual regions in tourism, since our country has quite a lot of places where objects of display of different

orientations are concentrated – natural, cultural: these are not only museums and architectural structures, secular and religious, but also ancient cities, ethnographic components, etc. Almost every state in the modern world has its own "tourist retro-markers" that evoke associations with a specific country: the pyramids in Egypt, the Dead Sea in Israel, the Great Wall of China in China, the Charles Bridge in the Czech Republic, the Champs Elysees in France, etc. Often, objects of display serve as very significant cultural components that contribute to interest in a particular vacation spot, "... an important unifying and mobilizing factor in establishing intercultural and interethnic communication" [2, p. 12].

One of the priorities in domestic tourism today is travel within the region of residence (about 30%), as this allows minimizing transportation costs, and mono-territories, more than ever, are interested in promoting their tourism resources and, accordingly, in attracting tourists and increasing the competitiveness of a particular locus. In this regard, for example, in the Lipetsk region, private entrepreneurs often act as investors, providing a certain level of tourism infrastructure using grant support (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 – Tourist and excursion flow in the Lipetsk region

At the same time, Lipetsk Region ranks first among the subjects of the Black Earth Region in terms of subsidizing tourism and the hotel business: three of their projects were supported (for the amount of 235.2 million rubles) to create modular non-capital accommodation facilities (OOO Vavilovo – modular guest houses in the

Oleniy nature park; OOO Retreat – expansion of the reserve territory). The Donskoy Les country club fund; ATP (T) Zhivaya Derevnnya (e-ATP (T) – expansion of the Zhivaya Derevnnya agrotourism complex).

An analytical review of preliminary data for the first quarter of 2024 shows a noticeable

increase in the number of trips throughout the Russian Federation. The first lines of analytics are traditionally occupied by the capital regions of the country, and the outsiders, as a rule, are the northern ones. At the same time, the Baikal region and the Republic of Adygea, Khabarovsk and Primorsky Krai, the Chechen Republic, etc. are gradually becoming favorites among travelers, which, in turn, will contribute to a more capacious presence of these regions in the tourism business. Representatives of the tourism industry in the difficult economic realities of today are quite rightly "betting" on "situational marketing", which is understood in the broad sense of the organization of weekend tours. Information about this is quite succinctly presented in the content of the portal "Russia.Travel", posted in a specially created section within the framework of the national project "Tourism and Hospitality Industry". Increasing the marketing attractiveness of domestic tours is currently achieved through the use of local socio-cultural technologies and innovative (or alternative) resources.

Modeling of non-standard ways of enhancing the marketing appeal of domestic tours, not excluding the use of traditional (unique) socio-cultural technological solutions for individual territories, is quite successful. Within the framework of various national projects both in the country as a whole and in its individual regions, multidirectional, multi-level "communication campaigns" are being implemented at this stage³.

In modern Russia, tourists continue to show interest in both active types of tourism, e.g. in Krasnaya Polyana and in the Dombai mountains, and the passive types, the most popular being, naturally, beach tourism in the "Russian subtropics".

At the same time, the transformation of domestic tourism in the Russian Federation, which occurred in the light of well-known events (the pandemic and the imposed sanctions), has identified the most attractive places in the regions of

Russia. One of them is the Baikal region, which has recently entered the top 10 leading regions actively involved in the development of domestic tourism, as it has unique natural and recreational resources (Lake Baikal) and is an interesting "platform" for intercultural communications, being in the center of diplomatic, industrial and trade interactions with Asian states. In our opinion, cultural, educational and gastronomic tours (which have already become traditional) with an emphasis on authenticity – "studying the culture of peoples through traditional cuisine" – and tasting tours continue to arouse no less interest, but at the same time new trends in the development of tourist destinations are emerging – tours with a reduced information background (the so-called "digital-detox"), astrotourism, "sleep tourism", "atypical" and "unexplored" travel routes, "concert tourism" are quite popular; tours with eco-initiatives, for example, "ecodiving", etc. are also in trend. At the same time, it should be noted that industrial tourism is not slowing down in popularity: travelers are showing an active interest in the "Promobot" enterprise in Perm, which specializes in the production of "service robots" for museums, clinics and hotels, in the Gzhel ceramics factory in the Moscow region, in the "Raketa" watch factory in St. Petersburg, in the metallurgical plant in Cherepovets and the cheese factory in Kaliningrad, which produces the classic "Tilsiter", etc.

However, in the development of domestic tourism in individual single areas of Russia, one should appeal to both current trends in tourist destinations and to retro traditions of hospitality, which concentrates in itself "elements of national culture, such as art, science, religion, history" [3, p. 24].

Despite the fact that the scientific community has not yet developed a clear understanding of the term, in the context of this study, "national content" should, first of all, be understood as a set of outstanding achievements of "...an independent and distinctive national culture, the

³ See for example: The project "Tourism and Hospitality Industry" (at the federal level); route-constructor "Estate Ring" (at the regional level).

preservation of national traditions, ... values that reflect the characteristics of the national character of the peoples living in the country” [1, p. 1].

In the process of studying the retro-block of tourist resources located in different subjects of the Russian Federation, general ones, characteristic of Russia as a whole, and special ones, allowing to individualize and emphasize the “faces with non-generic expression” of individual territories, are distinguished.

Thus, in the regions of the Ciscaucasia, beach and ski tourism are quite actively promoted, which occasionally use a retrospective excursus into the tradition of hospitality. In turn, cultural, educational and health types almost completely cover the retrospective focus in the tradition of hospitality.

Retro travel into the traditions of hospitality can be considered as components of individual directions of the tourism industry development in Kuban.

The creative life of the first Nobel laureate in literature, I. A. Bunin, served as an impetus for the development of the tourism industry in the center of Russia. The importance of a certain place in the formation of the "creative individuality" of the author of "Antonov Apples" undoubtedly forced the marketing of this region to concentrate in the corresponding direction and gave impetus to the development of cultural and educational tourism [9, p. 07013]. A professional retrospective excursus into the traditions of hospitality is certainly an effective means of expanding the possibilities of promoting individual single areas.

Conclusion

It is impossible to imagine socio-economic and political life in modern conditions without the tourism industry. In fact, it is this sector of the economy that can serve as a kind of "litmus test" that reflects the level of economic development of a particular regional territory. Of course, domestic tourism shows what infrastructure facilities are needed by a particular region to meet all the necessary needs of travelers, which, in turn, makes it possible to expand the range of jobs in various fields of activity related to the tourism industry. The demand for an excursion into the past (in the context of hospitality traditions) is currently due to various reasons, including the recent pandemic and numerous sanctions from the "collective West", which have affected the possibilities of outbound tourism and turned travelers' attention to domestic tourism content.

Attracting the exclusive retrocontent in the development of hospitality traditions of single territories during periods of serious geopolitical problems will make it possible to preserve not only the national identity of individual territories, but also to satisfy the interests and demands of travelers who want to broaden their horizons through knowledge of hospitality traditions both directly in their own places of residence and beyond. Such an approach is “strategically important”, since it partly determines not only the prospects for the development of tourism within the country, but also contributes to the promotion of tourist content of Russia in general.

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